

Enabling Model-Based Security Engineering - Automated Attack Tree Generation in ThreatGet

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Abstract: Security analysis as the initial step of security engineering is of utmost importance. Current approaches are mostly manual and neither connected to system engineering nor following established model-based approaches. We present here a novel approach to automatically derive Attack Trees based on a system model, enhanced with security-related information. The approach is based on STRIDE Threat Modeling, but utilizes a set of novel features to identify potential attack paths. With this, new regulations, requiring security analysis for more domains can be addressed and we enable system engineers to evaluate the security during design time and follow a risk-based security-by-design approach.

1 INTRODUCTION

With the increasing pressure on demonstrable security, rigour and traceable security engineering are necessary for many domains. Examples are the automotive domain, where new regulations like UN R155 and standards like ISO/SAE 21434 [4] require security-by-design, which has to be ensured before a new vehicle can be brought into the market. In a similar way, the European Cyber Resilience Act (CRA) [3] requires an even wider range of products with digital elements, including industrial control systems to follow security-by-design.

Model-based engineering can be used to address these new challenges for security engineering. We will present here an overview of the state of the art of security engineering, followed by new requirements on security compliance. After this, we will present our novel approach regarding model-based security analysis. This part will be concluded with a discussion on the next steps and open issues.

2 State of the Art

Cybersecurity analysis identifies risks by evaluating the impact and likelihood of attacks. All subsequent steps are based on this. A security-by-design approach aims to reduce risk to an acceptable level early

during development. Security Engineering can be divided into organization, processes and methods & tools.

2.1 Standards Regarding Security Engineering

Documents like the domain-independent NIST SP 800-160 on system security engineering [10] gives mostly guidance on organisational topics and processes with goals and work products. Methods are listed for the operational time of a system, but not for the initial engineering phases, e.g. regarding the analysis.

The ETSI Technical Specification ETSI TS 102 165-1 CYBER; Methods and protocols; Part 1: Method and pro forma for Threat, Vulnerability, Risk Analysis (TVRA) [5] defines a methodology for the analysis of systems and rating of risks but does not introduce automation or tooling.

Other, domain-specific, standards on security engineering like the IEC 62443 [13] contain guidance on integrating analysis into the overall process, but no method or tooling for cybersecurity analysis. Similar to the ISO/IEC 15408 and ISO/SAE 21434 [9] contain guidance on resulting work products and steps, but no methodology.

This is partially a result of the need to be applicable to many potential situations and also the knowledge that the lifetime of a standard, especially in a fast-moving field like security, might be longer than a method. Research and development might overtake a

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standard, therefore standards focus on slower-moving topics like organizational issues and processes. Recommendations on methods are mainly given as informative or in examples. An often-mentioned approach is Threat Modeling or STRIDE.

2.2 Literature Regarding Security Engineering

Threat Modeling combines a depiction of a system under consideration with a generic collection of known issues (the threat model) to identify specific issues for the system under consideration. Threat Modeling based on STRIDE, was integrated as an essential step in the Microsoft Security Development Lifecycle. Based on a depiction of the system and the STRIDE mnemonic, potential threats for each element are brainstormed [12].

Based on this initial approach, automation was developed like the Microsoft Threat Modeling Tool and the OWASP Threat Dragon [2] where the mapping of STRIDE to element is formalized in a threat model and the identification is automated, based on a diagram of the system. Threat Modeling was also later used for other topics like privacy (e.g. LINDUUN) [11].

Threat Modeling tries to identify all potential threats but without consideration of goals or interconnection of the threats. The initial manual approach was focused on threats per element and automation only extended this to threats considering at most two connected elements, e.g. identifying threats between at most two connected elements. Attack Trees start with an attack goal and try to identify potential paths an attacker could undertake to reach this goal [6]. While there is some work on formalizing Attack Trees [1] this is not yet aimed at an automated generation, but more at the evaluation. To summarize, while Threat Modeling is more concerned with identifying all potential threats, Attack Tree analysis is focused on identifying complete attack scenarios. In a study on security attack graphs, it was identified that this field suffers from inconsistency in naming, e.g. multiple terms are used to mean the same thing and inconsistency in representation [8]. Also an overview of pre- and post-conditions and their relation to Attack Trees was presented, but no connection to Threat Modeling or automation was given.

An example of the generic and not well-defined nature of Threat Modeling vs. attack modeling and the overall field of security analysis approaches is given in [14] where Threat Modeling, attack modeling and other methods are presented. We see here also the use of formal methods, which often bring the

challenge of adaptation in the security field. Formal methods, model-based engineering and security engineering require different foundations and it will be difficult for a security or system engineer to also gain proficiency in these not directly related fields while working on daily projects.

In our opinion, it will be necessary to automate a formal and model-based approach to security analysis. The method has to identify threats and potential attack scenarios. Engineering resources are restricted and security has to be focused on vulnerable parts of the system. Since in our experience, one of the favourable aspects of STRIDE-based Threat Modeling is the ease of use and restricted complexity, formalism has to be hidden.

3 Automated Attack Tree Generation

Our presented approach is based on an extension of Threat Modeling, which allows the automated generation of Attack Trees.

3.1 Extended Data Flow Diagram

The basic Microsoft Threat Modeling approach divides a system into four types of components: External Entity, Process, Data Store and Data Flow. Security-related properties can be defined for all components to specify their security-related behaviour and sub-types can be defined. **Data Flow** can be divided into the two sub-types of **Wireless Data Flow** and **Wired Data Flow**. An example of a property of a data flow would be encryption. Based on the granularity of the model and placement in the design process, values for this property could range from Boolean information (encryption = yes/no) to levels (encryption = no/weak/strong) to concrete technical details (encryption = no/AES-128/AES-256). In order to better support systems in the industrial domain, we introduced additional element types like a shared medium, which represents a wireless medium or a bus communication, e.g., all communication types where messages are not directed but accessible by all communication partners.

3.2 Introduction of Assets as Attack Goals

While Threat Modeling searches for threats to each element, an Attack Tree requires a target for the attacker. We introduce here the notion of assets. Assets

can be connected to elements or to connections and denote the processing, communication or storing of something of value to a stakeholder. Assets are targets for an attacker. An Asset needs one or more relevant cybersecurity properties (CIA = Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability). A violation of the cybersecurity property of an asset allows an attacker to reach an impact. Rating of impacts and order of cybersecurity properties can be adapted, based on the concrete system under analysis.

3.3 Differentiate Connections with Ports

Ports allow two significant enhancements regarding the representation of systems. They allow differentiating between endpoints of connections with their security measures. A device could have a wireless interface that requires authentication and a local diagnostic interface that does not require authentication but is behind a tamper-proof enclosure. In addition, while Data Flow Diagrams can be drawn on different levels of abstraction, there is no direct connection between these levels. Ports allow us to utilize, like in standard model-based engineering compositional diagrams and connect elements to their refinements.

3.4 Utilization of Post- and Pre-conditions

In order to generate an Attack Tree based on Threat Modeling results, we need to identify which threats are initially triggered and, based on the results, potential subsequent threats. We utilize a variant of contract-based design [7]. An initial set of threats without pre-conditions is used as starting points. These threats aim at reachable attack surfaces or initially vulnerable elements and result in the attacker gaining new capabilities (post-conditions). Based on these post-conditions next potential steps for an attacker are identified.

4 Application Example

The considered example is based on a typical industrial control system with an enterprise management layer, supervisory layer and field layer. The system diagram with one of the results of the security analysis is shown in 2. An initial analysis, without specified security measures, results in 337 threats. After an initial set of security measures (Enterprise Management Layer, Supervisory Layer and Local Field offer physical protection) we are able to reduce this

Figure 1: Industrial Control Architecture with potential attack path

to 64 threats. Further refinements, e.g. firewall rules for incoming traffic were able to reduce this to 40 threats. Generating potential attack trees for the defined Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) Asset in the Enterprise Management Layer showed a remaining attack path from the remote field. Table 2 shows the set of automatically identified threats with post and pre-conditions. The threats are derived by applying a formalized threat model to the system model. Based on required and provided capabilities threats are automatically combined. The initial vulnerability is an insecure wireless interface which allowed to access the communication. Malicious communication from the local field level can be masqueraded as regular traffic due to insufficient checking of incoming communication from the field devices level and reach the supervisory layer. An Engineer Station was not included in patch and update management and vulnerabilities could be used to access the ERP server on the Enterprise Management level. From a set of threat rules the following was automatically identified and combined:

Figure 2: Threat Model with post- and preconditions

Precondition	Rule	Postcondition	Element
	Attacker can access wireless interfaces without sufficient security	Access	Field network
Access	Attacker can gain control over connected elements with insufficient protection or patch status	Control	Control System, Intelligent Electronic Device (IED)
Control	Attacker can utilize pre-existing communication to send commands, if input is not checked	Access	Engineer Station
Access	Attacker can gain control over elements with insufficient protection or patch status	Control	Engineer Station
Control	Attacker can utilize pre-existing communication to send commands, if input is not checked	Access	Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) Server
Access	Attacker with access can violate confidentiality assets	Impact	Asset

5 Conclusion

We showed here an approach in which Threat Modeling can be connected to system engineering and enhanced to generate Attack Trees. Such approaches are necessary to achieve compliance with the increasing set of security regulations. Our society depends on the trustworthy and reliable operation of digital infrastructure and automated and easy-to-use approaches are required to ensure security.

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